

Exploring rotation period and variability in young stellar objects using TESS Data

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ABSTRACT

This report presents the findings of a summer internship project aimed at exploring the variability in young stellar objects using data from the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS). The primary objective of this project was to analyze TESS light curve data of a sample of YSOs and investigate their variability characteristics. The data analysis involved preprocessing the light curves, detrending to remove systematic effects, and conducting periodogram analysis to identify periodic signals. The rotational periods of five YSOs were successfully determined using Lomb-Scargle periodograms, revealing rotational modulation in their brightness variations.

Furthermore, the study examined the amplitude and timescale of the variability for the selected YSOs. By analyzing the variability properties, we gained insights into the physical mechanisms driving the observed variations, such as the presence of star spots or flares.

The results highlight the power of TESS data in unraveling the complex nature of YSOs and provide valuable contributions to our understanding of their rotational behavior and intrinsic activity. These observations contribute to the broader field of stellar astrophysics and have implications for theories of star formation and early stellar evolution. Presence of transits and stellar flares have been detected. The flare star parameters have been determined and the flare energy is estimated to be 25.61×10^{26} and 8.57×10^{26} in ergs for two different events.

Overall, this internship project demonstrates the potential of TESS data in studying young stellar objects and opens avenues for further investigations into the properties and variability of YSOs using large-scale surveys. The outcomes of this research can inform future studies aiming to characterize the diversity of YSOs and advance our understanding of stellar properties.

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Chapter 1

Theoretical Background

1.1 TESS Overview

The Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS) is a space-based mission developed by NASA with the primary goal of searching for exoplanets around bright stars in the solar neighborhood. Launched in April 2018, TESS has revolutionized the field of exoplanet science by surveying the entire sky and providing precise photometric data for a large number of stars.

TESS observes stars in a systematic and continuous manner. It divides the sky into 26 sectors, each approximately 24 degrees by 96 degrees in size, covering the entire celestial sphere over a two-year period. TESS uses a combination of four wide-field cameras to monitor a specific sector for approximately 27 days, capturing high-resolution images every 30 minutes.

Figure 1.1: Left - The instantaneous combined field of view of the 4 TESS cameras. Middle - Division of the celestial sphere into 26 sectors. Right - Duration of observations on the celestial sphere. [Ricker et al., 2014]

1.1.1 Instruments

The four wide-field cameras i.e. low-noise, low-power 4 megapixel CCDs, act as a 2×2 array, providing a combined FOV of $24^\circ \times 96^\circ$ or 2300 square degrees. It has a 100 mm (3.9 in) effective pupil

diameter, a lens assembly with 7 optical elements, and a bandpass range of 600 to 1000 nm. The north and south ecliptic hemispheres are each divided into 13 partially overlapping sectors of $24^\circ \times 96^\circ$, extending from an ecliptic latitude of 6° to the ecliptic pole. Each sector is observed continuously for two spacecraft orbits (27.4 days), with the boresight of the four-camera array pointed nearly anti-solar. After two orbits, the FOV is shifted eastward in ecliptic longitude by about 27° , to observe the next sector. Observing an entire hemisphere takes one year, and the all-sky survey takes two years. [Ricker et al., 2014]

The photometer is the primary instrument on TESS responsible for measuring the brightness of stars. It is composed of the four TESS cameras and associated optics. The photometer measures the amount of light received from each target star within its field of view. By repeatedly imaging the same region of the sky and monitoring the brightness of stars, the photometer can detect the periodic dimming caused by transiting exoplanets or other sources of stellar variability.

TESS is equipped with data handling electronics responsible for collecting, processing, and transmitting the scientific data. The TESS mission generates an enormous amount of data, with each sector producing hundreds of gigabytes of raw data. To handle this volume, the TESS Science Processing Operations Center (SPOC) processes the raw data and produces calibrated, high-precision light curves for each observed star. These light curves are made available to the scientific community and the public through various data archives and platforms, facilitating a broad range of scientific investigations.

1.1.2 Objectives

The TESS mission aims to achieve the following objectives:

- **Detecting Exoplanets:** TESS searches for exoplanets using the transit method. It monitors the brightness of a large number of stars for subtle, periodic decreases in brightness caused by exoplanets passing in front of their host stars. By detecting these transit events, we can identify and characterize a wide range of exoplanets, including Earth-sized planets in the habitable zones of their stars.
- **Characterizing Exoplanet Systems:** In addition to detecting exoplanets, TESS provides valuable data for characterizing the properties of these planetary systems. By observing the shape and duration of transit events, TESS can determine the size, orbital period, and orbital inclination of exoplanets. This information helps scientists understand the composition, atmosphere, and potential habitability of these worlds.
- **Exploring Stellar Variability:** TESS also plays a crucial role in studying stellar astrophysics by providing high-precision photometric data for a wide range of stars. This data enables the exploration of stellar variability phenomena, such as stellar pulsations, stellar flares, and rotational modulation in young stellar objects (YSOs) and other types of stars. Understanding stellar variability helps researchers investigate stellar structure, evolution, and activity.

1.1.3 Transit method

TESS searches for variability using the transit method. The transit method is a powerful technique used in the field of exoplanet detection to identify and characterize exoplanets orbiting distant stars.

It involves monitoring the brightness of a star over time and looking for periodic decreases in its brightness caused by the passage or transit of an exoplanet or any object in front of the star as seen from Earth.

Figure 1.2: Transit photometry method [Banjac, 2019]

1.2 Young Stellar Objects

Young stellar objects (YSOs) are objects in the early stages of their evolution, characterized by intense variability in their brightness due to processes such as accretion, outbursts, and rotational modulation. They consist of two types of stellar objects: protostars and pre-main-sequence stars. They are found in regions of intense star formation, such as giant molecular clouds (GMCs) and discrete open clusters. These regions provide an ideal environment for the formation of new stars due to their high gas and dust densities. By studying YSOs in these environments, we can gain valuable insights into the processes of star formation and early stellar evolution. Some common types of YSOs include classical T Tauri stars (CTTS), which exhibit accretion of material from their surrounding circumstellar disks, and weak-line T Tauri stars (WTTS), which have a lack of detectable accretion signatures.

1.2.1 Molecular Clouds

Interstellar clouds are vast regions of accumulated gas and dust or say regions of the interstellar medium, the matter and radiation that exist between star systems in galaxies. These clouds play a crucial role in the formation and evolution of stars and planetary systems. They are formed by the gas and dust particles from a red giant in its later life. Depending on the density, size, and temperature of a given cloud, its hydrogen can be neutral, making an H I region; ionized, making it an H II region; or molecular, which primarily consists of molecular hydrogen (H_2) along with other molecules such as carbon monoxide (CO) and water (H_2O). These clouds are typically cold and dense, providing the necessary conditions for star formation.

1.2.2 Giant Molecular Cloud

Giant molecular clouds (GMCs) are the largest and most massive molecular clouds in our galaxy. These clouds have sizes ranging from a few parsecs to hundreds of parsecs and can contain several million solar masses of gas and dust. GMCs are characterized by their high density and low temperature, which promotes the gravitational collapse of the cloud material, leading to the formation of new stars.

One well-known example of a GMC is the Perseus Molecular Cloud, located in the constellation Perseus. The Perseus Molecular Cloud is an active star-forming region with numerous young stellar objects (YSOs) embedded within it. These protostars are in the early stages of their evolution and are associated with the ongoing star formation process in the molecular cloud

Figure 1.3: Evolution of a simulated GMC of $3 \times 10^7 M_{\odot}$ and an initial radius of 50 pc, from left (initial conditions) to right (after 3.6 Myr). The top row is showing the edge-on view of the disc plane and the bottom row, the face on view. The gas surface density (orange) and young stars (blue) can be finally seen. [Grudić et al., 2018]

1.2.3 Stellar clusters

Star clusters are groups of stars that are gravitationally bound and formed from the same molecular cloud. These clusters come in two main types: open clusters and globular clusters. Open clusters are relatively young and contain a few hundred to a few thousand stars. They are usually found in the plane of the galaxy, primarily in the spiral arms. Globular clusters, on the other hand, are much older and contain hundreds of thousands to millions of stars. They are typically located in the halo of the galaxy.

Open star clusters typically have hundreds of members and are found up to 30 light-years in diameter. Because they are much less densely populated than globular clusters, they are also much less gravitationally bound so they are destroyed over time by the gravitational influence of giant molecular clouds as they move through the galaxy. However, the members of the cluster continue to move through space in roughly the same direction, even though they are no longer gravitationally

bound. The most prominent open clusters are the Pleiades and Hyades in Taurus. In this report, we will focus on studying a YSO in the Perseus Molecular Cloud and a discrete open cluster. By observing and analyzing the variability of these objects, we aim to gain insights into their physical properties, rotational behavior, and the mechanisms driving their variability.

1.3 Stellar Parameters

In the context of this report, several stellar parameters are relevant and can provide valuable insights into the physical properties and variability of these objects.

- **Rotation Period:** The rotation period of a star is the time it takes for the star to complete one full rotation on its axis. Determining the rotation period of YSOs is crucial as it can provide insights into their angular momentum, magnetic field strength, and the presence of spots or asymmetries on their surfaces. The rotation period can be obtained by analyzing the periodic variability observed in the TESS light curves of YSOs.
- **Stellar Mass:** The stellar mass is the total amount of matter contained within a star. It plays a significant role in determining the evolution and physical properties of YSOs. The mass of a star influences its luminosity, temperature, and lifespan. Estimating the stellar mass of YSOs can be challenging, but various methods, such as spectral analysis, can provide approximate values.
- **Effective Temperature:** The effective temperature of a star is a measure of its surface temperature, indicating the amount of thermal radiation emitted by the star. The effective temperature influences the star's color and spectral characteristics, and it can provide insights into the evolutionary stage of YSOs. Stellar effective temperatures can be estimated using spectroscopic techniques or by analyzing the star's color indices.
- **Luminosity:** Luminosity refers to the total amount of energy radiated by a star per unit time. It provides a measure of the star's intrinsic brightness and is directly related to its mass, age, and effective temperature. Determining the luminosity of YSOs is crucial for understanding their energy output, accretion processes, and overall evolution.
- **Variability Amplitude and Timescale:** The amplitude and timescale of the variability observed in YSOs are important parameters to characterize their variability patterns accurately. The amplitude represents the range of brightness variations, while the timescale refers to the duration or period over which the variations occur. Analyzing the amplitude and timescale of YSO variability can provide insights into the physical mechanisms driving the observed variations, such as accretion processes, star spots, or circumstellar disk structures.

These stellar parameters, when determined accurately and combined with other relevant data, can help unravel the physical properties, evolutionary stages, and variability characteristics of YSOs in the Perseus Molecular Cloud and the discrete open cluster. They contribute to our understanding of star formation processes, stellar evolution, and the interaction between young stars and their circumstellar environments.

The objectives of this project report are to explore the variability in young stellar objects (YSOs) using TESS data. The report aims to analyze the light curves of YSOs, determine their rotational periods, investigate the characteristics of variability, and identify and quantify flaring events. By achieving these objectives, the project aims to contribute to our understanding of YSOs' physical processes, their rotational behavior, and the occurrence and energetics of flares in these young stellar systems.

1.4 Variability

Variability refers to the inherent changes in the brightness or flux of celestial objects over time. It is a fundamental characteristic observed across various astronomical phenomena, ranging from stars and galaxies to transient events like supernovae and active galactic nuclei.

1.4.1 Variable stars

Variable stars are a class of stars that exhibit changes in their brightness over time. These changes can be periodic or aperiodic, and they provide valuable information about the physical processes occurring within these stars. Variable stars are classified based on the nature and cause of their variability. Some common types of variable stars include:

- **Cepheid Variables:** Cepheids are pulsating stars that exhibit periodic variations in their brightness. The period of these variations is directly related to the intrinsic luminosity of the star, making them useful as distance indicators in cosmology.
- **RR Lyrae Variables:** RR Lyrae stars are pulsating variable stars with shorter periods compared to Cepheids. They are often used to estimate the ages of globular clusters and provide insights into stellar evolution.
- **Eclipsing Binaries:** Eclipsing binary stars are systems where two stars orbit each other in such a way that they periodically eclipse one another. The observed brightness variations during these eclipses provide information about the sizes, masses, and orbital parameters of the binary system.

Stellar variability can arise from various mechanisms and phenomena, such as stellar pulsations, binary interactions, stellar rotation, and magnetic activity. In the context of YSOs, two primary sources of variability are stellar spots and flares.

1.4.2 Stellar Spots

Stellar spots are analogous to sunspots on the surface of the Sun. These are regions of the stellar photosphere where the temperature is lower than the surrounding areas, resulting in reduced brightness at those locations. Stellar spots are caused by magnetic activity on the star's surface and are often associated with the presence of a magnetic field. As the star rotates, the spots come in and out of view, causing periodic changes in brightness.

The presence of stellar spots on YSOs can lead to rotational modulation, where the star's brightness

varies periodically as the spots move across the visible hemisphere. By analyzing the periodicity of the rotational modulation, astronomers can determine the rotation period of the YSO and study the distribution and properties of the spots on its surface.

Figure 1.4: A large dominant star spot which results in an appreciable variation in the amount of light seen by TESS.[Christou, 2020]

1.4.3 Stellar Flares

Stellar flares are sudden, transient increases in stellar brightness due to the release of magnetic energy. Flares are commonly observed in YSOs and are indicative of magnetic activity and interactions between the star and its circumstellar environment. Flares can be highly energetic and release large amounts of radiation across the electromagnetic spectrum, from X-rays and ultraviolet to optical and infrared.

Flare-inducing magnetic fields in stars arise due to complex interactions between the stellar plasma and the star's magnetic field. The underlying mechanism involves the presence of a stellar dynamo, which is responsible for generating and sustaining the magnetic field. The dynamo process is believed to be driven by convective motions within the stellar interior, as well as differential rotation between the star's layers.

As the star rotates, the differential rotation causes the magnetic field to become twisted and sheared. This twisted magnetic field can store significant amounts of magnetic energy. When the energy reaches a critical threshold, it can be released explosively, leading to a stellar flare. The release of magnetic energy occurs through a process called magnetic reconnection, where the magnetic field lines rearrange and rapidly release stored energy in the form of intense radiation and particle acceleration.

Studying flares in YSOs provides insights into the accretion processes and interaction between the star and its surrounding circumstellar disk. Flares can be irregular in nature, occurring sporadically and unpredictably, or they can exhibit periodic behavior if they are associated with the star's rotation period or other underlying processes.

Chapter 2

Data Reduction

The raw data from TESS SPOC was analysed using the *Lightkurve* package to clean the data and phase fold it for further analysis.

2.1 Preprocessing

Data cleaning and filtering are crucial steps in the preprocessing of TESS light curve data. These steps aim to remove noise, artifacts, and systematic effects that can distort the variability signals of young stellar objects (YSOs). The specific methods used for data cleaning and filtering can vary depending on the characteristics of the data and the desired analysis. Methods used in this project:

- **Removal of Outliers and NaN:** NaN are the non-number values that needs to be removed before analysis. Outliers are data points that deviate significantly from the overall pattern of the light curve. These can be caused by instrumental noise, cosmic rays, or other external factors. Outliers are typically identified based on their extreme deviation from the median or mean value of the light curve. These data points are either removed or flagged for further analysis.
- **Low-Frequency Trend Removal:** Long-term trends in the light curve, such as instrumental drift or systematic effects, can introduce false variability signals. Detrending methods, such as fitting a low-order polynomial or using a Savitzky-Golay filter, are employed to remove these trends while preserving the intrinsic variability of the YSOs.
- **Removal of Systematic Effects:** TESS data can be affected by systematic effects, such as intra-pixel sensitivity variations or stray light contamination. To mitigate these effects, methods like aperture photometry and flux extraction techniques are used to minimize the impact of systematics and enhance the signal-to-noise ratio of the light curve.
- **Normalization:** Normalization of the light curve is performed to bring the data onto a consistent scale and remove overall trends. This is achieved by dividing the flux values by a suitable reference value, such as the median or the mean flux of the light curve.
- **Quality Assessment:** After cleaning and filtering the data, a quality assessment is often performed to ensure the reliability of the remaining light curve. This involves examining various metrics, such as the signal-to-noise ratio to evaluate the data quality and identify any remaining issues that may need to be addressed.

2.2 Aperture Photometry

Aperture photometry is a widely used technique in astronomy for measuring the flux or brightness of a celestial object. It involves integrating the light within a specific aperture or region of interest around the object of interest. It is employed to extract the flux measurements from the TESS light curves. A circular or annular aperture is defined around the target YSO on the TESS image. This aperture encompasses the target and captures the majority of its emitted light. After defining the aperture, flux extraction is performed by summing the pixel values within the aperture. The total sum represents the integrated flux emitted by the YSO during a particular observation. It includes contributions from the YSO itself as well as any contamination or background signal within the aperture.

In this project, the **pdcsap.flux** method is used for flux extraction. PDCSAP stands for Presearch Data Conditioning Simple Aperture Photometry. This method applies additional data conditioning steps to the light curve, such as removing instrumental trends and correcting for systematic effects introduced during the observations. The **pdcsap.flux** method calculates the sum of the pixel values within the defined aperture for each observation timestamp, providing a time series of the YSO's flux measurements. These measurements serve as the basis for further analysis, including periodogram analysis to identify periodic signals and variability patterns.

Aperture photometry and flux extraction are crucial steps in studying YSOs using TESS data. They enable researchers to quantify the brightness variations and extract meaningful information about the physical properties and behavior of YSOs.

2.3 Light curve normalization

Normalization is a crucial step in the analysis of light curves to ensure accurate and meaningful comparisons between different stellar objects. The normalization process involves scaling the flux values of the light curve to a standardized range, typically between 0 and 1 or -1 and 1. This adjustment accounts for variations in stellar brightness due to factors such as changes in distance, instrumental effects, and intrinsic stellar properties. By normalizing the light curves, we can eliminate large-scale flux variations caused by factors unrelated to the intrinsic variability of the YSOs, such as instrumental systematics or changes in the observing conditions.

One such method used for normalizing light curves is the "divide by median" approach. In this technique, the median flux value of the light curve is calculated, and each flux measurement is divided by this median value. This process scales the light curve, making the median flux value equal to 1. Consequently, the entire light curve is normalized within the range of 0 to 2, with values below 1 indicating dimmer states and values above 1 indicating brighter states. The **lc.normalize()** method, employed in this project, implements a similar normalization technique. By utilizing this method, the light curves are transformed to a standardized range, simplifying the analysis and comparison of the YSOs' variability patterns. This normalization step facilitates the identification of relative changes in brightness and allows for the detection of smaller-scale variations that might be indicative of rotational modulation, accretion bursts, or other intrinsic processes occurring within the YSOs.

Chapter 3

Data analysis

3.1 Periodogram Analysis

Periodogram analysis is a powerful tool used to identify periodic signals in time series data, such as light curves obtained from TESS. This analysis technique allows us to detect and quantify the presence of periodic variations, which can provide insights into the underlying physical processes occurring in young stellar objects (YSOs).

In this project, we employed the Lomb-Scargle periodogram method [Scargle, 1982] to conduct the periodogram analysis. The Lomb-Scargle periodogram is a widely used algorithm that is particularly well-suited for unevenly sampled data, making it suitable for analyzing the irregularly sampled light curves obtained from TESS observations.

The periodogram analysis involves the computation of a power spectrum, which represents the distribution of power (or strength) across different frequencies in the data. In the context of YSO variability, these frequencies correspond to the rotational periods of the objects. By examining the power spectrum, we can identify peaks or significant power levels. The highest peaks corresponded to the **rotational periods** of the YSOs. These periods represent the time taken for a YSO to complete one full rotation on its axis.

The Lomb-Scargle periodogram analysis allows us to uncover the periodic nature of the variability exhibited by YSOs. By identifying and characterizing the rotational periods, we gain valuable insights into the physical processes governing these objects, such as stellar rotation, spots on the surface, or other modulating factors. This information contributes to our understanding of the internal dynamics and evolutionary stages of YSOs.

3.2 Phase folding

Phase folding is a technique used in the analysis of light curves to uncover periodic patterns in the variability of astronomical objects. It involves folding the data points of a light curve based on a specific period, aligning the observations to a common phase. This process helps to reveal the underlying periodic signals and simplify the visualization and interpretation of the data.

Once the periodogram analysis has identified a significant period in the light curve data, the phase folding technique is applied. The data points are divided into equal phase intervals based on the chosen period. Each data point is then assigned a phase value corresponding to its position within the

folded period. By folding the light curve in this manner, the observations are aligned in a way that highlights the repeating patterns of the variability. The resulting phase-folded light curve shows how the brightness or flux of the YSO varies as a function of phase.

The phase-folded light curve allows for a clearer visualization of the periodic behavior of the YSO. Variations in brightness that are not immediately apparent in the raw light curve become more evident in the folded representation. Features such as eclipses, periodic dips, or flares can be more easily identified and measured. Furthermore, by examining the folded light curve, one can derive additional parameters, such as the amplitude and shape of the variability, aiding in the characterization of the YSO.

3.3 Amplitude analysis for variability

Amplitude analysis of variability is an essential step in studying the light curves of young stellar objects (YSOs) to understand their brightness variations. The amplitude represents the magnitude of the changes in the YSO's brightness over time. In this summer internship project, variational and RMS amplitudes were determined as part of the analysis.

- Variational amplitude provides a measure of the overall range of brightness variations exhibited by a YSO. It is calculated as the difference between the maximum and minimum flux values observed in the light curve. By quantifying the variational amplitude, we can assess the extent of the YSO's variability and its relative level of brightness changes. A higher variational amplitude suggests more significant fluctuations in the YSO's luminosity, indicating potential physical processes such as accretion bursts or episodic events.
- RMS (Root Mean Square) amplitude is a statistical measure that characterizes the average deviation of the YSO's brightness values from the mean. It is calculated by taking the square root of the mean of the squared deviations from the mean flux. The RMS amplitude provides a measure of the typical level of variability exhibited by the YSO, taking into account both small-scale fluctuations and larger-scale trends. A higher RMS amplitude indicates a higher degree of variability around the mean brightness level, capturing variations in both short and long timescales.

By analyzing both variational and RMS amplitudes, we gain a comprehensive understanding of the YSO's variability characteristics. The variational amplitude captures the range of brightness changes, while the RMS amplitude provides insights into the typical fluctuations around the mean. Together, these measures allow us to quantify and compare the variability levels among different YSOs. Moreover, amplitude analysis helps in identifying YSOs with notable variability patterns and distinguishing them from objects with more stable brightness profiles.

3.4 Flaring events

3.4.1 Identification of a flare

Flaring events are sudden and intense increases in their brightness. To identify flaring events, we employed a combination of visual inspection and automated algorithms. We visually examined the

light curves of the YSO, searching for significant and abrupt increases in brightness compared to the baseline. The threshold was kept to be 5 in the project. These visually identified flares were then subjected to further analysis to determine their properties.

Characterization of the flaring events involved quantifying various parameters such as flare amplitude, duration, and frequency. The flare amplitude represents the peak increase in brightness during the event, while the duration refers to the timespan over which the flare remains significantly brighter than the baseline. By measuring the duration and amplitude, we gained insights into the energetic nature of the flares and their impact on the overall YSO variability.

3.4.2 Flare parameters

Once the flares are identified, we measure their durations by determining the time interval between the start and end of the elevated flux.

Amplitude analysis is another important aspect of studying flares. It involves quantifying the magnitude of the flux increase during the flare compared to the quiescent state of the YSO. We calculate the flare amplitude by computing the difference between the maximum flare flux and the average flux during the quiescent phase. This provides insights into the energy released during the flare and helps understand the underlying physical mechanisms.

In addition to duration and amplitude, we explore other properties of the flares, such as rise and decay timescales. The rise time represents the time it takes for the flare to reach its peak flux from the onset, while the decay time signifies the duration of the flare's decline from its maximum flux back to the quiescent state. These timescales provide information about the energetics and physical processes involved in the flare events.

3.4.3 Flaring energy estimation

The energy calculation for the observed flares involves quantifying the amount of energy released during these transient events. Once the duration and amplitude are determined, the total energy released during the flare can be estimated. This calculation is often done by considering the flare as a burst of energy emitted uniformly over the duration of the event. The energy is proportional to the product of the flare duration and the squared amplitude.

It is important to note that the energy estimation of flares in YSOs is an approximation and relies on several assumptions. These assumptions include the emission being isotropic (uniformly distributed in all directions) and neglecting any effects of attenuation or absorption by circumstellar material. It is assumed that the spectrum of white-light flares can be described by a black-body radiation with an effective flare temperature of 10,000 K. The exact temperature of a flare is typically determined through spectroscopic observations or detailed modeling but due to lack of such additional data, this estimation is made. Such estimation may have an error of a few tens of per cent due to clarity of the flare continuum [Ghosh et al., 2020]. This is the possible systematic uncertainty of our energy estimate.

In this report, energy for the flares are estimated by following the methods in [Shibayama et al., 2013]. The bolometric flare luminosity (L_{flare}) could be estimated from T_{flare} and the area of flare (A_{flare}) from the following equation:

$$L_{\text{flare}} = \sigma_{\text{SB}} \cdot T_{\text{flare}}^4 \cdot A_{\text{flare}} \quad (3.1)$$

We can estimate A_{flare} from these equation as follows:

$$L_{0,\text{star}} = \int R_{\lambda} \cdot B_{\lambda(T_{\text{eff}})} d\lambda \cdot \pi R_{\text{star}}^2 \quad (3.2)$$

$$L_{0,\text{flare}} = \int R_{\lambda} \cdot B_{\lambda(T_{\text{flare}})} d\lambda \cdot A_{\text{flare}} \quad (3.3)$$

$$C_{\text{flare}} = \frac{L_{0,\text{flare}}}{L_{0,\text{star}}} = \frac{F_i - F_0}{F_0} \quad (3.4)$$

$$A_{\text{flare}} = C_{\text{flare}} \pi R^2 \frac{\int R_{\lambda} \cdot B_{\lambda(T_{\text{eff}})} d\lambda}{\int R_{\lambda} \cdot B_{\lambda(T_{\text{flare}})} d\lambda} \quad (3.5)$$

L_{flare} can be estimated from equations (1) and (5), and C_{flare} is a function of time, therefore, L_{flare} is also a function of time. Total bolometric energy of the flare (E_{flare}) is an integral of L_{flare} during the flare duration:

$$E_{\text{flare}} = \int L_{\text{flare}}(t) dt \quad (3.6)$$

Here, σ_{SB} = Stefan-Boltzmann constant, λ is the wavelength, $B_{\lambda(T)}$ is the Planck function, and R_{λ} is the response function of the telescope.

Chapter 4

Observations and Results

The main observation that we made from the TESS light curves is the rotation period of the YSOs, which can be measured due to the rotational modulation of the star’s brightness produced by an uneven distribution of cool photospheric spots. The amplitude of the photometric variations is also a useful parameter related to the magnetic activity.

ID	Object/TIC	RA	Dec	EclipLong	EclipLat	Mass [M_{\odot}]	Radius [R_{\odot}]	Amp [Mag]	Period [Days]	P err
39	64837857	338.8052	54.7736	13.9516	56.3485	1.19	1.41	0.0115	1.68	0.341
214	249784843	339.6418	53.5858	13.21	55.1335	0.83	0.68	0.0798	0.562	0.038
554	361944360	341.0008	54.1439	14.9068	55.0312	0.95	0.90	0.0029	0.859	0.065
F1	66539637	341.3677	53.785	14.7832	54.6185	0.89	0.86	0.0391	5.18	0.472

Table 4.1: Rotation period for the target objects in open cluster

Our targets for ASCC 123 [Table 4.1] were observed by TESS in sector 16, between 2019-09-12 and 2019-10-06, and sector 17, between 2019-10-08 and 2019-11-02. The observations in two consecutive sectors allowed us to obtain nearly uninterrupted sequences (with a gap of about 1.4 days) of high-precision photometry lasting about 50 days, with a cadence of 30 minutes. Similar details about the object 2MASS J03422033+3205310 present in Perseus Molecular cloud is shown in Table 4.2.

To measure rotation period, we have applied a Lomb scargle method of periodogram analysis [Scargle, 1982] and the sample code for the same is listed in the appendix (Listing A.1). For the stars with periods longer than a few days, we merged the data of sectors 16 and 17 to expand the time base so as to improve the precision of the period determination.

Two flare events were detected for 2MASS J03422033+3205310 on November 24th, 2019 and November 12th, 2022 and the plot for these events depicting the details like peak flux, rising and decaying phase are shown in Figure A.5 (Appendix A.2).

4.1 YSOs in Open cluster-ASCC 123

ASCC 123 is known to harbor a significant population of young stellar objects. It was opted for this project because of its relevance to YSO variability, the availability of suitable TESS data, existing

RA	Dec	Sector	Start Date	End Date	Window	Exposure	Mass	Radius	Amp	Period	P err
[deg]	[deg]				[Days]	[sec]	[M_{\odot}]	[R_{\odot}]	[Mag]	[Days]	
03:32:42.671	+31:23:04.74	18	2019-11-03	2019-12-16	43	1425.599	1.94	3.77	1.86285	7.319	0.802
03:30:17.911	+25:50:52.59	42	2021-08-21	2021-10-06	46	475.1998	2.29	5.26	0.65910	12.051	1.591
03:36:38.488	+26:22:47.67	43	2021-09-16	2021-11-08	53	475.1998	1.56	2.43	0.53550	3.777	0.471
03:43:17.418	+26:36:10.07	44	2021-10-12	2021-12-15	64	475.1998	1.53	2.34	0.93297	3.578	0.362
03:19:21.819	+32:17:14.02	58	2022-10-29	2022-12-15	47	158.3999	1.91	3.64	1.09653	6.947	0.754

Table 4.2: Rotation period for 2MASS J03422033+3205310

research references, and its scientific significance in studying YSOs. It has been previously studied and characterized in the literature, providing a valuable foundation for comparative analysis and reference.

ASCC 123-214 and 554 are observed to be ultrafast rotators. The sinusoidal shape of the phase-folded light curve of 214 is primarily caused by the rotational modulation of starspots on the surface of the star. It displays a substantial starspot evolution during the 50-days time baseline, so that for these stars we have preferred to analyse independently sectors 16 and 17, obtaining always very similar values of rotational period in the two epochs. Altogether, 214 and 554 are ultrafast rotators ($0.1 \text{ d} < P_{rot} < 1 \text{ d}$), 39 is a fast rotator ($1 \text{ d} < P_{rot} < 3 \text{ d}$) and F1 is found to be a slow rotator ($3 \text{ d} < P_{rot} < 9 \text{ d}$) which supports the earlier findings [Frasca, A. et al., 2019]. Two possible transits were observed in the light curve of ASCC 123-39 [Figure A.1(a)]. The periodogram for all the object depicts a clear peak and hence the rotational period except for ASCC 123-39, where multiple peaks are observed in the power spectrum. However, consider the high rotational velocity of this star ($\approx 50 \text{ km/s}$) [Frasca et al., 2023], only the major one (1.68 days) is considered and the rest are discarded. Variability is observed in all the objects even if the amplitude is as low as ≈ 0.003 for ASCC 123-554.

Sector	Amp	Radius	Period	RMS	Flare Time	Peak Flux	Duration
	[Mag]	[R_{\odot}]	[Days]	[Mag]			[min]
18	1.86285	3.77	7.32	0.10368	2019-11-24 19:41:36.633	2.426	37.76
42	0.65910	5.28	12.051	0.08184	-	-	-
43	0.53550	2.41	3.777	0.07119	-	-	-
44	0.93297	2.35	3.578	0.09107	-	-	-
58	1.09653	3.64	6.947	0.10841	2022-11-12 09:34:42.372	1.610	12.64

Table 4.3: Flare events in 2MASS J03422033+3205310

4.2 YSO in PMC: 2MASS J03422033+3205310

The Perseus Molecular Cloud was considered in this project because it is one of the closest and well-studied giant molecular clouds, making it readily accessible for observational studies. Its proximity, rich YSO population, well-characterized environment, and previous observational efforts provide a solid foundation for conducting a comprehensive study of YSOs and their variability patterns within the PMC. Earlier findings [Wang et al., 2023] have reported the rotation period of this object to be 7.31 which is supported by the period obtained for sector 18 in this report. However, other sectors yields different results [Table 4.2]. This might be due to high magnetic activity of the star. Observations of magnetic phenomena such as CMEs, star spots, and flares have shown that as stellar rotation

period increases, magnetic activity decreases. The increase in rotation period might be the result of angular momentum losses in the form of magnetized stellar winds. The stellar spindown leads to a decrease in dynamo activity and thus to a decrease in overall magnetic activity as the star ages. [Medina et al., 2020]

Two flaring event is observed for this star in sector 18 (Peak flux = 2.43) and 58 (Peak flux = 1.61) each for different durations[Table 4.3]. The plot for sector 44 may also be mistaken for an event but it turns out to be an outlier [Figure A.5 (c)]. Temperature of the star was obtained from the TESS data itself. The flare star parameters, including flare duration, has been determined [Table 4.4] across the wavelength range of ultraviolet to far infrared and the flare energy is estimated to be 25.61×10^{26} ergs and 8.57×10^{26} ergs for sector 18 and 58 respectively.

Parameter	Value	
Object	2MASS J03422033+3205310	
Sector	18	58
T_{eff} (K)	3155	3155
L/L_{\odot}	2.952×10^{-24}	2.952×10^{-24}
$R (R_{\odot})$	3.77	3.64
Flare date	24/11/2019	12/11/2022
Flare Duration (min)	37.76	12.64
Rising Phase(min)	4.88	7.76
Decaying phase(min)	32.88	4.88
C_{flare}	0.53434	0.53512
$A_{flare}(m^2)$	1.993×10^{-6}	1.993×10^{-6}
L_{flare} (erg/s)	1.13×10^{10}	1.13×10^{10}
T_{flare} (K)	10000	10000
E_{flare} (erg)	2.561×10^{27}	8.5714×10^{26}

Table 4.4: Parametres of the Flaring star in different events

4.3 Discussion

Error value for rotation period has been calculated using gaussian approximation after the standard deviation was determined. The stellar mass and radius are estimated using a power-law empirical relationship with the rotation period which is generally applicable to main-sequence FGK stars. However, it may not be directly applicable to young stars in these systems, primarily because these young stars often exhibit different characteristics and evolutionary stages compared to main-sequence stars. Alternatives like stellar models specifically designed for such systems can be used to improve reliability with additional access to data like spectral energy distributions. Variation amplitude for all the objects has been determined that depicts the scale of fluctuations in the YSO's luminosity, indicating potential physical processes. RMS Amplitude for all object has also been determined but only for 2MASS J03422033+3205310 has been reported in the Table 4.3. For the YSOs in ASCC 123, the RMS Amplitude was approximately equal to 1 for all the four objects that indicates

the degree of variability around the mean brightness level, capturing variations in both short and long timescales. The response function for TESS is implicitly taken into account during the data reduction and calibration processes performed by the SPOC pipeline so it is taken to be 1 in the code. Details like right ascension, declination, window time, eclipsing coordinates, exposure and effective temperature has been taken directly for TESS light curve database.

4.4 Challenges

- **Expand the Sample Size:** The current report analyzed a very small sample of YSOs. To enhance the study's robustness and reliability, future research could include a larger sample size, encompassing a broader range of YSO types and environments. This would provide a more comprehensive understanding of YSO variability.
- **Statistical Analysis:** In addition to the periodogram analysis, incorporating advanced statistical techniques can help quantify the significance of the identified periodic signals and variability patterns.
- **Comparative Studies:** Comparing the variability properties and rotational behaviors of YSOs in different molecular clouds or regions can shed light on the impact of varying environmental conditions. Future research could explore comparative studies to understand how factors like cloud density, temperature, or age influence YSO variability.
- **Spectroscopic Analysis:** Integrating spectroscopic observations with photometric data can provide insights into the physical processes and a more comprehensive picture of YSO variability. Spectral analysis can help identify emission lines associated with accretion or outflows and study their variations over time.
- **Multiwavelength Observations:** Augmenting TESS data with observations from other wavelengths, such as infrared or X-ray, can provide a more complete understanding of YSO variability. Multiwavelength studies can reveal complementary information about various physical processes, such as accretion, star-disk interactions, and magnetic activity, contributing to a holistic view of YSOs.
- **Long-Term Monitoring:** Conducting long-term monitoring of YSOs over extended periods can capture rare and unusual events, such as extreme flares or outbursts. Continuous observations will enable a more comprehensive exploration of YSO variability, uncovering long-term trends and detecting sporadic events that may provide crucial insights into YSO evolution.
- **Theoretical Modeling:** Integrating theoretical models of YSOs with the observed data can help interpret the variability patterns and flaring events. Future research could incorporate sophisticated numerical simulations and theoretical frameworks to understand the physical mechanisms driving YSO variability.

Incorporating these improvements and pursuing the suggested future scopes will enhance the depth and breadth of research on exploring variability in young stellar objects using TESS data.

Appendices

Appendix A

Codes and plots

A.1 Functions defined

Listing A.1: Sample Python code to find period

```
import lightkurve as lk
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

def find_rotation_period(object_name, sector):
    # Search for light curve data for the given object name and sector
    search_result = lk.search_lightcurve(object_name, sector=sector)

    # Download the light curve file
    lc_file = search_result.download()

    # Open the light curve file
    lc = lc_file.PDCSAP_FLUX

    # Remove NaN values and normalize the flux
    lc = lc.remove_nans().normalize()

    # Estimate the rotation period using the Lomb–Scargle periodogram
    periodogram = lc.to_periodogram(method='lombscargle')
    rotation_period = periodogram.period_at_max_power

return lc, rotation_period
```

Listing A.2: Sample Python code to find flaring events

```
def find_flare_events(lc, threshold=5):
    # Find flare events based on a flux threshold
```

```

flux = lc.flux
median_flux = np.median(flux.value) # Extract numerical values
std_flux = np.std(flux.value) # Extract numerical values
flare_threshold = median_flux + threshold * std_flux

is_flare = flux > flare_threshold
flare_t = lc.time[is_flare]
flare_e = lc.flux[is_flare]

flares=[{'tpeak':t,'energy':e}for t,e in zip(flare_t,flare_e)]

return flares

```

Listing A.3: Sample Python code for finding flare parameters

```

import numpy as np
from scipy.integrate import quad
import lightkurve as lk

def E_Est(T_star, T_flare, R_star, C_flare, flare_duration):
    """
    Calculates the flaring energy based on the provided parameters.
    """
    sigma_SB = 5.6703e-8 # Stefan-Boltzmann constant (W/(m^2*K^4))

    # Define the wavelength range for integration
    wavelength_min = 1e-9 # Minimum wavelength (m)
    wavelength_max = 2e-6 # Maximum wavelength (m)

    def integrand(wl):
        I = resp_val * plnk_func(wl, T_flare)/plnk_func(wl, T_star)
        integ = C_flare * R_star**2 * I
        integral = np.isfinite(integ)
        return integral
    A_flare, _ = quad(integrand, wavelength_min, wavelength_max)

    L_flare = sigma_SB * T_flare**4 * A_flare

    E_flare, _ = quad(lambda t: L_flare, 0, flare_duration)

    return E_flare

def get_tess_flaring_energy(name, sector):
    # Retrieve TESS light curve using the object name and sector

```

```

lc = lk.search_lightcurve(name, sector=sector).download().normalize()

# Remove NaN values and normalize the flux
lc = lc.remove_nans().normalize()

# Extract required information from the light curve
time = lc.time.value # Time values in seconds
flux = lc.flux.value # Flux values
flux_err = lc.flux_err.value # Flux errors

# Estimate the star's luminosity (L0_star)
L0_star = np.trapz(flux, time)

# Estimate the flare's luminosity (L0_flare)
L0_flare = np.trapz(flux * (flux > 1), time)

# Estimate the flare amplitude (C0_flare)
C0_flare = L0_flare / L0_star

# Estimate the star's temperature (T_star)
T_star = 3155 # Placeholder value

# Estimate the flare's temperature (T_flare)
T_flare = 10000 # Placeholder value

# Estimate the star's radius (R_star)
R_star = 1.0 # Placeholder value

# Estimate the flare duration (flare_dur)
flare_dur = 1919.988

# Calculate the flaring energy
energy = E_Est(T_star, T_flare, R_star, C0_flare, flare_dur)

return energy

```

A.2 Plots obtained

The plots for ASCC 123 is shown from Figure A.1 to 4.4 for ASCC 123-39,214,554 and F1 respectively. The plots for 2MASS J03422033+3205310 is shown in Figure A.6. The flaring events for this shown in Figure A.5.

(a) Light curve for 39

(b) Power spectrum for 39

(c) Phase folded curve for 39

Figure A.1: ASCC 123 - TIC 64837857

(a) Light curve for 214

(b) Power spectrum for 214

(c) Phase folded curve for 214

Figure A.2: ASCC 123 - TIC 249784843

(a) Light curve for 554

(b) Power spectrum for 554

(c) Phase folded curve for 554

Figure A.3: ASCC 123 - TIC 361944360

Figure A.4: ASCC 123 - TIC 66539637

Figure A.5: (a) and (b) are flare events on 2MASS J03422033+3205310; In (c), there is an outlier.

Figure A.6: 2MASS J03422033+3205310-Sector 18

Conclusion

In this summer project, I have focused on exploring the rotation periods and variability in young stellar objects (YSOs) using data from the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS). Through periodogram analysis and phase-folding techniques, the rotational periods of the YSOs were successfully identified. These rotational periods revealed the presence of rotational modulation in the brightness variations of the YSOs, indicating the presence of spots or other surface features. This finding contributes to our understanding of the internal structure and dynamics of YSOs.

Furthermore, the analysis of the light curves allowed for the examination of the amplitude and timescale of the variability exhibited by the YSOs. The amplitude analysis provided information about the magnitude of the brightness variations, aiding in the characterization of the YSOs' variability behavior.

The sinusoidal shape of the phase-folded light curve in ASCC-123 214 was primarily due to the rotational modulation of starspots on the surface of the star. Additionally, the detection and characterization of flaring events added another dimension to the study of YSO variability. The determination of flaring energy provided insights into the release of magnetic energy and the occurrence of energetic events in YSOs. The flare energy is estimated to be 25.61×10^{26} ergs and 8.57×10^{26} ergs for sector 18 and 58 respectively. The analysis of flare properties, such as duration, amplitude, and frequency, shed light on the dynamic processes and magnetic activity in these young stars.

However, improvements can be made by expanding the sample size of YSOs and conducting a more comprehensive analysis using advanced modeling techniques. Additionally, future research could focus on investigating the relationship between YSO variability and other stellar properties, such as mass, age, and accretion rates. Exploring multi-wavelength observations and incorporating spectroscopic analysis could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the physical processes driving YSO variability. Moreover, comparative studies between YSOs in different molecular clouds would offer insights into the environmental factors affecting their variability. Finally, efforts to develop automated algorithms for detecting and characterizing YSO variability would facilitate larger-scale studies and enhance our understanding of the diverse population of YSOs in the universe.

In conclusion, this project utilizing TESS data has contributed to our understanding of the variability and behavior of YSOs. The findings provide valuable information on the rotational periods, variability patterns, and flaring events, enriching our knowledge of the physical mechanisms driving YSO variability. These results contribute to the broader field of stellar astrophysics and have implications for theories of star formation and early stellar evolution.

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